

EXEMPTION FROM ADMINISTRATIVE LIABILITY AS A RESULT OF NECESSARY DEFENSE

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Abstract: This article analyzes the concept of necessary defense and the legal grounds for exempting a person from administrative liability as a result. It also examines the legal assessment of actions committed in a state of necessary defense, its conditions and limits, and its place in current legislation. The article highlights that the state of necessary defense is one of the important legal instruments for protecting the rights and interests of an individual, as well as the interests of society and the state. Furthermore, it outlines the significance of exemption from administrative liability in cases of necessary defense within law enforcement practice and presents some proposals for its improvement.

Keywords: necessary defense, administrative liability, exemption from liability, administrative offense, legal grounds, legal protection, legislation, law enforcement practice, individual rights, administrative law.

The institution of necessary defense is considered one of the oldest and most fundamental institutions of the legal system. It recognizes an individual's right to protect oneself, other persons, and the interests of society and the state from unlawful encroachments. In a modern rule-of-law state, necessary defense is established not only in criminal law but also in the sphere of administrative liability as a ground for precluding liability. In the context of exemption from administrative liability, the institution of necessary defense is a practical expression of the principles of humanism, culpability, and proportionality.

According to Article 37 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an act committed in a state of necessary defense is not considered a crime, provided that the limits of necessary defense were not exceeded. This provision defines exceeding the limits as a defense that is disproportionate to the nature and degree of danger of the attack. At the same time, a person is not deprived of the right to necessary defense even if they have the opportunity to escape by other means. This rule indicates the absolute nature of the right to defense.

The same approach is reflected in Article 18 of the Code of Administrative Liability. This article stipulates that an act committed in a state of necessary defense is not considered an administrative offense. However, in the administrative-legal context, necessary defense is applied in a somewhat narrower scope compared to criminal law, as administrative offenses encompass acts with a lower degree of social danger.

In academic literature, necessary defense is interpreted not as an exception to the principle of culpability, but as its logical continuation. This is because, in a state of necessary defense, a person's actions are socially justified and do not contain the constituent elements of an offense. Claus Roxin describes necessary defense as "the law that protects the law," considering it a mechanism for restoring social justice.[1]

Z The role of necessary defense in the basis of exemption from administrative liability lies in the fact that the actions of a person may formally have signs of an administrative offense, but

their social content is justified by law. For example, a physical act committed in a public place may externally resemble hooliganism, but if it is committed for the purpose of protection from aggression, administrative liability does not arise.

The main theoretical problem related to necessary defense is the question of defining its boundaries. In criminal law, exceeding the boundaries is more clearly regulated, while in administrative law, this issue is more formed through judicial practice. Article 2.7 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Russian Federation defines necessary defense as a circumstance excluding liability. The resolutions of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Russia indicate that when assessing the criteria of necessary defense, the reality, proximity, and degree of danger of the aggression are taken into account[2].

According to statistics, although the total number of administrative cases in the courts of the Russian Federation in 2022-2023 amounted to millions of indicators, cases of termination of a case on the basis of necessary defense are rare. Reports from the Judicial Department indicate that cases of exclusion of liability, including necessary defense, constitute a small percentage of the total number of cases considered.[3] This indicates the exceptional nature of necessary defense.

The differences between necessary defense in criminal law and necessary defense in administrative law are manifested in several directions. Firstly, in criminal law, necessary defense is more often applied to serious offenses, and in administrative law, it is more often manifested in the context of minor offenses. Secondly, in criminal law, exceeding the boundaries can create an independent corpus delicti, while in administrative law, the issue of administrative liability usually arises. Thirdly, if in criminal law necessary defense completely excludes criminal liability of a person, in administrative law it means the absence of the elements of an administrative offense.

Necessary defense is also recognized as a universal institution in international legal systems. In the practice of the European Court of Human Rights, the right to self-defense is interpreted as one of the fundamental human rights. "Engel and Others v. Netherlands," the court noted that administrative sanctions may in some cases be criminal in nature and therefore criminal law standards should be applied when assessing circumstances excluding liability. In the German legal system, necessary defense (Notwehr) is recognized as a basis for excluding liability not only in criminal law, but also in the legislation on administrative offenses. German scholar Hans-Heinrich Jescheck considers necessary defense an active form of protecting legal order and interprets it as an exception to state monopoly[4].

Thus, as a result of necessary defense, the institution of exemption from administrative responsibility is theoretically based on the principle of guilt, the criterion of proportionality, and the principles of humanism. Although it is close to the institution of necessary defense in criminal law, it differs in scope of application and consequences. This institution must be carefully evaluated in law enforcement practice, as the issue of exceeding the boundaries can lead to subjective interpretations.

The theoretical foundations of the institution of necessary defense are fully manifested in how it is applied in practice. Determining the state of necessary defense in the context of exemption from administrative liability requires a high level of legal assessment from judicial authorities. Because an action that can be assessed as an administrative offense based on external signs may actually be socially justified. Scientific literature notes that an incorrect

assessment of necessary defense can lead to a restriction of a person's right to constitutional protection[5].

Although cases of necessary defense are relatively rare in the judicial practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the analysis of existing cases shows that courts mainly focus on three criteria: the reality of the attack, its immediate nature, and the degree of danger. Necessary defense is not applied if the aggression is fictional or provocative. This is consistent with Article 37 of the Criminal Code, which states that "incitement to the desire to attack is not recognized as necessary defense."

Practice in the Russian Federation is also formed in this direction. In the reports of the Judicial Department of the Russian Federation for 2022, it was noted that the total number of administrative cases amounted to more than 6 million, and the share of cases terminated on the grounds of excluding liability is relatively low[6]. This indicates the exceptional nature of necessary defense. At the same time, Article 2.7 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Russian Federation clearly defines the state of necessary defense.

In judicial practice, the issue of proportionality of aggression plays a key role in assessing necessary defense. If the defensive action absolutely does not correspond to the nature and degree of danger of the aggression, it is recognized as exceeding the limits of necessary defense. In criminal law, such a situation can give rise to an independent corpus delicti, while in administrative law, the issue of administrative liability usually arises. In this regard, there is a significant difference between the institution of necessary defense in criminal law and necessary defense in administrative law.

In the German legal system, the Notwehr institution is widely interpreted. In German judicial practice, a person is not obligated to evade an attack within the framework of necessary defense. This is explained by the "Rechtswahrungsprinzip" - the principle of protection of rights[7]. In the sphere of administrative offenses, the state of necessary defense also excludes liability. However, German lawyers emphasize the criterion of proportionality.

In the French legal system, the institution of "légitime défense" has a general character in criminal and administrative sanctions law. Jean Pradel argues that necessary defense is a limited exception to the state's monopoly on punishment, as the individual protects the legal order instead of the state in a given situation. This approach is also applied in the field of administrative law. Although the institution of self-defense is widely used in criminal law in the US legal system, it is also taken into account to a certain extent in the field of administrative law. According to the principle of due process, imposing an administrative penalty on a person acting in self-defense may be considered contrary to the principle of justice. Joshua Dressler considers the criteria of voluntariness and proportionality as the central elements of necessary defense[8].

The main differences between necessary defense in administrative and criminal law are manifested in the following. Firstly, in criminal law, necessary defense is applied to grave socially dangerous acts, and in administrative law, it manifests itself in the context of relatively minor offenses. Secondly, in criminal law, exceeding the boundaries can entail independent criminal liability, while in administrative law, it is usually limited by administrative sanctions. Thirdly, in criminal law, the procedural guarantees of the institution of necessary defense are broader, and in administrative law, a simplified procedure is applied.

In Uzbekistan's practice, when assessing necessary defense situations, the provisions of Article 37 of the Criminal Code apply comparatively to administrative cases. This serves to

ensure a unified legal approach in practice. At the same time, the institution of exemption from administrative responsibility practically ensures the principles of humanism and proportionality.

In conclusion, practice and comparative analysis show that the institution of exemption from administrative liability as a result of necessary defense has a universal legal nature, its content is close to the institution of criminal law, but differs in scope of application and legal consequences. A clear understanding of these differences is crucial for making fair decisions in law enforcement practice.

To fully understand the issue of exemption from administrative liability as a result of necessary defense, it is necessary to analyze it not only within the framework of national legislation, but also from the point of view of international legal standards and comparative law. In modern law-governed states, administrative sanctions are becoming increasingly "quasi-criminal" in nature, and there is a tendency to apply criminal law standards even to cases that exclude liability[9].

In the practice of the European Court of Human Rights, the "Engel criteria" are used to determine whether administrative sanctions are of a criminal nature. "Engel and Others v. Netherlands," although the administrative penalty was officially defined as administrative, it was established that criminal-legal guarantees could be applied depending on its nature and severity[10]. This means that high procedural standards are required when assessing circumstances that exclude liability, such as necessary defense.

"A. Menarini Diagnostics S.R.L. v. Italy," the court also noted that in cases where the amount of administrative fines is large, they can be considered a criminal charge[11]. These decisions indicate the need to ensure guarantees of fair trial, the principle of guilt, and proportionality in the system of administrative responsibility. If a person's actions in a state of necessary defense are criminally justified, punishment with an administrative penalty may contradict human rights standards.

In the German legal system, the Law on Administrative Offenses (Ordnungswidrigkeitengesetz) developed in close connection with criminal law. German scholars, discussing the nature of administrative sanctions, emphasize that in some cases they acquire criminal-legal content. From this point of view, it is proposed that the institution of necessary defense should be applied in the field of administrative law, as in criminal law. In the French legal system, the institution of "cause d'irresponsabilité" has general provisions in criminal and administrative sanctions law. Jean Pradel argues that necessary defense is an exception to the state's monopoly on punishment, since the individual protects the legal order instead of the state in a given situation[12]. This concept strengthens the theoretical basis of the institution of exemption from administrative responsibility.

In the US legal system, administrative sanctions are applied by federal agencies, and due process requirements apply to them. Joshua Dressler stated that the main condition for liability is the presence of voluntary action[13]. If a person acted in self-defense and their actions were proportional, the application of administrative sanctions against them contradicts the principle of justice.

The concept of restorative justice is widely used in the legal systems of Canada and New Zealand. This approach prioritizes the restoration of social balance, not punishment[14]. If a person defends social order in a state of necessary defense, not punishment, but the legal justification of their actions is considered a fair solution.

There are opinions in scientific discussions about the "quasi-criminal" nature of administrative sanctions. Some scholars argue that in the case of large administrative fines, criminal-legal guarantees must be applied to them[15]. This means that a high level of evidence and legal analysis is required when assessing the state of necessary defense.

Although the application of the institution of necessary defense in administrative law is similar in content to the institution of criminal law, its scope of application is narrower. In criminal law, necessary defense is applied to grave socially dangerous acts, while in administrative law, it manifests itself in the context of relatively minor offenses. At the same time, in criminal law, exceeding the boundaries may entail independent criminal liability, while in administrative law, it is usually limited by administrative sanctions.

Analysis of international experience shows that the institution of exemption from administrative liability as a result of necessary defense has a universal legal nature. It is based on the principles of humanism, proportionality, and guilt. In this regard, it can be seen that national legislation does not lag behind international trends.

Thus, international standards and scientific views confirm that the institution of necessary defense has the same significance in administrative law as in criminal law. It strengthens the principles of the rule of law by ensuring the individual's right to self-defense.

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